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Research of professional motivation peculiarities of future economics teachers in the field of vocational education and training

Korvat, Larysa

Ukraine, Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadym Hetman, l_korvat@ukr.net

Shkoda, Tetiana

Ukraine, Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadym Hetman, tnshkoda@ukr.net

Abstract

The aim of this paper is to disclose the peculiarities of the choice motives of the economics teacher's profession in the field of vocational education and training (VET) by the students of the specialty "Vocational Education (Economics)" at Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadym Hetman (KNEU) with a number of psycho-diagnostic methods. The results obtained using the methods of E.H. Schein, A. Rean, J.L. Holland and the revealed statistically significant correlation coefficients are analysed in detail by the authors. It is concluded that the motivation of students has its peculiarities, on the basis of which it is recommended to predict and improve the education and training of future economics teachers in the field of VET.

Keywords

professional motivation; motivation of future teachers of economics; career orientation; educational motivation; professional orientation

1 Introduction

Young people, choosing a sphere of future professional activity, do not simply decide on what they are going to make for life, but also determine their way of life. Motives and goals of the individual determine the vector of its activity, the extent of inclusion in various activities, educational in particular.

Understanding what drives a person, what motives lie at the heart of his behaviour and actions, you can develop an effective system of forms and methods of managing its learning and professional development. Knowing the ways in which motives and value orientations can be put into action, one can predict the prospects of a young person in those or other areas of his professional activity.

2 Problem

The VET teacher is an important educational specialty, but despite the needs of the society in such teachers, those wishing to receive this specialty every year becomes less and less. One of the important directions of solving this problem may be studying the motivation of those students who have chosen their future professional activity as the economics teacher in the field of VET.

3 General provisions on motivation for professional development

One of the key concepts of this research is the notion of motivation. It is comprehensively studied in modern researches (Han, Yin, 2016; Panisoara et al, 2010). In relation to motivation of the professional formation of future VET teachers in the field of economics, the authors proceed from the definition that motivation is the internal dynamic, energetic impulses (motivators) of the individual to the activity and certain behaviour. Motivation of professional formation is multifaceted and multidimensional. On one hand, the same activity can be defined by several motives, on the other hand, it is integral, because it is precisely in the unique combination of individual motives that determine the peculiarities of activity, and in this case, the peculiarities of professional formation. The motives of the activity can be realized or not realized, yet they are decisive as to why the person acts exactly this way.

4 Psycho-diagnostic research of motivation of the professional formation of future teachers of economics

4.1 Research methods

There were taken the following research tools as psycho-diagnostic methods:

1. The method "Career Anchors" (Edgar H. Schein) to study the individual hierarchy of career orientations of students
2. The method for studying the student's educational and professional motivation (A. Rean et al.) to study the structure of students' motivation
3. The method of studying the professional orientation of students (John L. Holland)

To process the obtained results, the average values (\bar{X}) and percentages (%) were calculated for all the indicators found in the study, as well as the correlation coefficients between all the indicators.

The sample was comprised of students studying by the specialty "Vocational Education (Economics)" at KNEU. The study covered 72 people during their first year of study.

4.2 Peculiarities of career orientations

The method "Career Anchors" is developed on the basis of career anchors theory by E.H. Schein. "Career Anchors" are value orientations, social settings, interests, which are socially driven incentives for activities, inherent in each person. Major career orientations are (Schein, 1986):

1. Technical/functional competence
2. Managerial competence
3. Autonomy/independence
4. Security/stability
5. Entrepreneurial creativity
6. Service/dedication to a cause
7. Pure challenge
8. Lifestyle

The first position by the importance of surveyed orientations was taken by the career orientation "Security/stability" ($\bar{X}=7.3$), the second one – "Lifestyle" – ($\bar{X}=6.8$), the third one – "Service/dedication to a cause" ($\bar{X}=6.6$).

Let's consider the interpretation of leading career orientations. Prevalence of such leading career orientation as "Security/stability" was found in 92% of the students in the general sample. Such result, in the authors' opinion, is related to the specifics of contemporary socio-economic reality, in particular the fact that the present situation in Ukraine cannot be characterized as stable and predictable due to economic and political changes that lead to a lack of long-term prospects for young people. Obviously, in this situation, students consider career stability as particularly valuable. It means that the respondents seek to meet the need for security, and predict future life events. They believe that it is best to work in such an organization, which provides a long term of work, has a good reputation, looks reliable.

The "Lifestyle" orientation, ranked second, has a significant level of manifestation for 88% of students. The essence of this orientation is the desire to maintain the harmony between personal life and career.

The third place was taken by the career orientation "Service/dedication to a cause" ($\bar{X} = 6.6$; 77%). This value orientation is inherent in people who are engaged in their business because of the desire to realize in labour activity the main values that are important for an individual.

The unexpected result was that the career orientation "Technical / functional competence" turned out to be in the last place $\bar{X} = 4.1$ (27%). This can be explained by the fact that the essence of this career orientation is related to the interest in the content of professional activity, the availability of skills and achievements in a particular industry, the desire to be a specialist in this sphere. However, the students still do not have a holistic view of their professional activities. Another reason for the lack of interest in the content of professional activity is that at the present stage, students obtain higher education, but they do not plan to work by the specialty.

4.3 Peculiarities of educational and professional motivation

The method for studying the student's educational and professional motivation (A. Rean, V. Yakunin, N. Badmayeva) allows from another angle to study the motivation of students, in particular, the importance of individual aspects of professionally directed educational activities. The main motives that can be diagnosed with this method are (Badmayeva, 2004):

1. Communicative motives
2. Professional motives
3. Educational and cognitive motives
4. Broad social motives
5. Motives for creative self-realization
6. Motives for avoiding failure
7. Motives for prestige

The most significant indicators of student's educational and professional motivation are analysed further.

It was revealed that among the respondents the first place by the significance was taken by the professional motives - ($\bar{X} = 3.6$), the second position was taken by communicative motives ($\bar{X} = 3.4$), the third position belonged to social motives ($\bar{X} = 3.1$) and educational-cognitive motives ($\bar{X} = 3.0$).

In general, the obtained results can be explained by the fact that students are focused on acquiring professional knowledge and a certain level of qualification. Professionalism is a leading motive for studying students in higher education, however, this process is simultane-

ously associated with the desire to be involved in the communication process that accompanies academic activities, as well as the ability to learn the chosen professional field, gain a wide range of professional and general knowledge and be involved in the student and professional community, have a certain social status in communication, education, etc.

4.4 Peculiarities of professional orientation

The method by J.L. Holland serves to diagnose the professional orientation of the individual. According to this method there are six personality types (Holland, 1997): Realistic, Investigative, Artistic, Social, Enterprising and Conventional.

The statistical processing of the results of psychodiagnosis by J.L. Holland's method reflect the dominance among the respondents of artistic and social professional orientation ($\bar{X} = 7.9$), followed by conventional ($\bar{X} = 7.5$), entrepreneurial ($\bar{X} = 7.1$), realistic ($\bar{X} = 6.3$), and intellectual ($\bar{X} = 5.2$) orientations. This result to a certain extent reflects the general social tendencies of popularity of certain spheres of professional activity. Through the prism of J.L. Holland's theory, such results can be regarded as partly favourable for the future economics teacher of in field of VET, since the Social/Conventional code, which reflects the content of the profession of economics teacher, occupies the second position in the general formula for the professional orientation of students of the sample. The domination of the artistic type must be taken into account in the organization of the educational process, creating conditions for the realization of its needs.

5 Analysis of significant correlations of the research

The research of correlations between the obtained results has some significance (Sidorenko, 2002), since they reflect the peculiarities of the motivation of professional formation in the sample.

Calculations of correlations' coefficients between indicators obtained by the methods of E.H. Schein and A. Rean allowed revealing a significant level of correlation between the individual indicators presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Correlation's coefficients between the indicators of career orientations and educational and professional motivation

E.H. Schein's method	Method of A.Rean, V.Yakunin, N.Badmayeva						
	Com- municative mo- tives	Mo- tives for avoiding failure	Motives for pres- tidge	Pr ofes- sional mo- tives	Mo tives for creative self- realiza- tion	Edu cational and cog- nitive motives	So- cial motives
Techni- cal/functional competence	0,41*	0,40*					
Managerial competence	0,40*	-	0,40*				
Auton- omy/independenc e							- 0,45*
Secu- rity/stability			0,42**				

Service/dedication to a cause	- 0,47**	0,4 0*	0,4 0*
Pure challenge			
Lifestyle		- 0,47**	0,44**
Entrepreneurial creativity			

* $p \leq 0,05$; ** $p \leq 0,01$

Calculations of the correlation coefficients between the indicators by the methods of E.H. Schein and J.L. Holland are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Correlation's coefficients between the indicators of career orientations and professional personality type

E.H. Schein's method	J.L. Holland's method					
	Realistic	Investigative	Social	Conventional	Enterprising	Artistic
Technical/functional competence						
Managerial competence	- 0,40*				0,40*	
Autonomy/independence						
Security/stability	0,64**				-0,44**	
Service/dedication to a cause		0,40*		-0,51**		
Pure challenge				-0,40*		
Lifestyle					-0,40*	
Entrepreneurial creativity	- 0,40*			-0,41**		

* $p \leq 0,05$; ** $p \leq 0,01$

No significant correlations were found between the indicators of J.L. Holland and A. Rean's methods.

6 Conclusions and future perspectives of the research

The conducted research allows the authors to conclude that the students who have chosen a specialty of the economics teacher in the field of VET have certain motivational peculiarities that need to be taken into account in the process of their professional education and training. To answer the question of how much these peculiarities are inherent to the future teachers of

the economy, it is worth researching the motivational peculiarities of future teachers of other specialties and students of other specialties in general.

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Biographical notes

Larysa Korvat, Ph.D. in Psychology, associate professor at Department of Pedagogy and Psychology of Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadym Hetman. Scientific interests: psychology of vocational education, psychological training of students, development of professional competencies, personality psychology.

Tetiana Shkoda, Ph.D. in Economics, Scholar of the Scholarship Foundation of the Republic of Austria (Postdocs) in 2019 at Vienna University of Economics and Business, and associate professor at Department of Personnel Management and Labour Economics, Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadym Hetman. Scientific interests: human capital management, competence-based education and professional development of employees.